

FLEXURAL BEHAVIOUR OF ANISOTROPIC COMPOSITE DISCS SUBJECTED TO THREE-POINT SUPPORT BENDING TESTS

J. P. Nunes, A. S. Pouzada and C. A. Bernardo

Department of Polymer Engineering, Universidade do Minho, 4800 Guimarães, Portugal

SUMMARY: In this work, discs supported on three points were loaded at the centre to determine the flexural stiffness of composites produced from a Sheet Molding Compound (SMC/C-R) and a Carbon/Polycarbonate (C/PC) towpreg using different laminate stacking sequences. In this loading condition, the experimental results show that the flexural behaviour of the composites depends on several factors, such as fibre orientation, laminate stacking, surface waviness and moulding temperature. The experimental results were compared with those obtained from the finite element program Algor. The FEM analysis has shown to be a useful tool to describe the fibre orientation and the laminate stacking sequence in the composite. However, differences up to 13% were found between the experimental and simulated values obtained for the composite flexural stiffness.

KEYWORDS: flexural stiffness, 3-point support bending test, carbon/polycarbonate composites, Sheet Molding Compounds, flexural behaviour of discs, finite element analysis.

INTRODUCTION

The flexural stiffness of anisotropic composite plates subjected to pure bending in any direction is usually calculated using the flexural engineering constants directly derived from the laminate normalised flexural compliance matrix [1, 2]. Depending on support conditions, complex states of bending may result in service on composite plates and shells. Some of these bending situations can be specially severe to long fibre composites due to their lower stiffness across the fibre direction. Furthermore, as non-predictable multidirectional solicitations are generated in the laminate, the composite flexural behaviour is difficult to describe.

In this work, anisotropic discs of two different composite materials were loaded at the centre and subjected to the 3-point support bending test to assess and compare their flexural stiffnesses. An unidirectional carbon fibre polycarbonate matrix (C/PC) towpreg and a Sheet Molding Compound (SMC/C-R), with layers reinforced with continuous and randomly distributed glass fibres, were used. Discs with diameters of 200 and 105 (mm) were produced by compression moulding using four different temperatures. The influence of the processing temperature on the flexural behaviour of the discs was investigated. To assess the influence of the fibre direction on the flexural stiffness, the composite discs were bent with the continuous fibres direction varying with respect to the position of the supports. Finally, the properties of

the laminates' plies were determined and used in the finite element software program Algor (Algor Inc., Pittsburgh, U. S. A.) to generate data for comparison with the experimental results.

THEORY

Accordingly to Bassalli [3], the vertical deflection, δ , of an isotropic elastic disc loaded at the centre and supported in three points regularly distributed along the periphery is given by:

$$\delta = \frac{3 \cdot F}{2\pi \cdot h^3} \frac{1-\nu^2}{E} R^2 B(\nu) \quad (1)$$

where $B(\nu)$ is a function of the Poisson's ratio, ν :

$$B(\nu) = \frac{4}{(1-\nu)(3+\nu)} \left(2 \ln 3 - \frac{\pi}{27} (1+\nu)(\pi + 3\sqrt{3}) \right) + \frac{1}{2} \frac{(\nu-1)^2}{(3+\nu)(1+\nu)} \quad (2)$$

and,

- F - applied load
- R - radius of the circumference where the supports are located
- E - elastic modulus, and
- h - disc thickness

Thus, by making $S_o = \frac{F}{\delta}$ (actually the slope of the force/deflection trace at low strain), the *flexural stiffness* of the plate, $C = \frac{E}{1-\nu^2}$, can be directly derived from the force/deflection slope as:

$$C = \frac{3}{2\pi \cdot h^3} R^2 B(\nu) \cdot S_o \quad (3)$$

In the case of the actual testing, the Bassali expression is not applicable exactly as the disks overhang from the supports. Pouzada *et al.* [4, 5] developed experimentally a correction factor for the force/displacement slope of the Bassali equation (Eqn. 3). Accordingly, the slope in the experimental set-up is related to S_p as:

$$S_p = \frac{S_o}{0.59 \times \left(1 - e^{-4.1 \frac{\Delta R}{2R}} \right) + 1} \quad (4)$$

where,

- S_o - slope of the force/displacement curve obtained on disc bending tests, and
- ΔR - radial overhang (Fig. 1)

In spite of the explicit dependence of the *flexural stiffness* on the Poisson's ratio, its influence is minimal for most engineering materials, where ν varies between 0.2 and 0.5. In this range, the value of $B(\nu)$ varies between 1.66 and 1.72.

In this work, the assessment of the influence of the various parameters in the flexural behaviour was made in terms of a "reduced" flexural stiffness, $C_R = \frac{C}{B(\nu)}$, given by:

$$C_R = \frac{3}{2\pi \cdot h^3} R^2 \cdot S_p \quad (5)$$

EXPERIMENTAL

Materials

A dry powder coating unit developed at Clemson University (South Carolina, USA) [6-9] was used to fabricate unidirectional C/PC towpregs with 25% fibre volume content using a polycarbonate powder (Makrolon 2458) from Bayer and PAN based carbon fibres (Thornel T300/12/NT) from Amoco.

A commercial Sheet Molding Compound from Menzolit (28 LS 33745 202/11), based on an unsaturated polyester reinforced with E-glass fibres in a volume content of 30%, was used in the production of the SMC/C-R discs (200 mm in diameter and 2.5 mm thick). This material consists of two equal thickness layers with different reinforcements: one reinforced with continuous glass fibres and the other with 25 mm long chopped strand fibres.

Sample Preparation

Both C/PC and SMC/C-R plates were produced by hot compression moulding at four different temperatures using an 800 kN SATIM press.

Before compression moulding, a technique described elsewhere [10-12] was used to fabricate unidirectional C/PC. The C/PC performs were placed into a $117 \times 112 \times 2$ (mm) mould mounted in the press and pre-heated during 10 minutes at the temperatures ranging from 220 to 280 °C. The compression pressure was set at 8 MPa and maintained during 10 min. The mouldings were allowed to cool down to room temperature in the mould. Discs for testing with a diameter of 105 mm were cut from the C/PC plates.

The SMC/C-R discs were directly obtained from a pre-heated mould mounted between the platens of the press at temperatures ranging from 130 to 160 °C. A pressure of 10 MPa was maintained during 3 min to allow material curing before mould opening to eject the discs.

Three-Point Support Bending Tests

The rig for the three point flexural test as shown in Fig. 1 was mounted on an Instron 1122 testing machine with a 500N load cell. The tests were carried at the cross-head speed of 1 mm/min. The vertical displacement was measured at the central point of the disc with a LVDT displacement transducer with an accuracy of 1 μ m.

Fig. 1: Schematic diagram of the 3-point support flexural test (from [4])

12 SMC/C-R and C/PC discs from each moulding temperature condition were tested using the three supports located on 176 mm and 93.5 mm diameter circumferences, respectively.

The anisotropy induced by the fibre orientation in the flexural stiffness was assessed for both composites. This was done by rotating the discs to obtain three different alignments of the unidirectional fibres with respect to the position of the supports. As Fig. 2 shows, the discs were placed in the supports with the fibres aligned at angles γ of 0° , 15° and 30° with respect to the radial position of one of the supports and the centre of the disc. Four discs were tested each direction up to a deflection of approximately 2 mm to minimise the effect of membrane stresses.

Fig. 2: Composite disc loading conditions. 1- fibre direction; 2- direction of reference

FEM Simulations of Composite Discs Flexure

The derivation of an analytical solution for the bending of an anisotropic thin centrally loaded disc supported in three points regularly distributed along the circumference is not practical. Therefore the prediction of the flexural performance was based in simulations made using the FEM software Algor.

Figure 3 shows the finite element mesh for the SMC/C-R discs. The models for both composites consist of triangular elements with an aperture of 7.5° and a common vertex at the centre of the discs and quadrilateral elements elsewhere. A total number of 1004 and 480 elements were used in the definition of the SMC-R and the C/PC discs, respectively.

Fig. 3: FEM model to simulate the SMC/C-R disc bending

Three nodes located in the circumferences at a radial distance from the centre of 46.75 mm and 88 mm were used to define the supports in the C/PC and SMC/C-R discs, respectively. The vertical displacement (x-direction) was calculated for a load of 35 N applied vertically at the centre of the discs.

The composite material-type element was selected in the software to enter the elastic properties of the laminate plies, which are shown in Table 1.

Table 1: In-plane elastic properties of the composite plies

PROPERTY	Units	MATERIAL		
		C/PC	SMC/C-R	
		Unidirectional ply	Unidirectional ply	Randomly reinforced ply
Longitudinal modulus (E_1)	GPa	51.80	29.60	8.87
Transverse modulus (E_2)	GPa	3.13	6.03	8.87
Shear modulus (G_{12})	GPa	1.13	2.32	3.41
Poisson's ratio (ν_{12})	-	0.35	0.28	0.30

For the C/PC composite, the properties were derived from micromechanical models [1, 2, 13] using the fibre volume content and the raw materials tensile properties. The tensile properties of the PAN carbon fibres and polycarbonate matrix were determined by single filament tests. In the case of the SMC/C-R composites, the properties of the plies were also derived from the

fibre volume content, the raw materials and the composite tensile properties determined from ISO 3268 tensile tests.

The C/PC laminate was considered as composed by twenty 0.1 mm thick plies with properties defined in Table 1.

Two types of plies, with a thickness of 1.25 mm, were considered for the SMC/C-R laminates. One, had the properties already defined in Table 1 for the unidirectional ply at the top of the laminate, 0° oriented in relation to laminate referential. The other was isotropic, with the properties mentioned in Table 1 for the randomly reinforced ply at the bottom of the laminate.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A plot of experimental results obtained for flexural stiffness of the C/PC and SMC/C-R against the fibre orientation angle (γ) is shown in the Figure 4.

The SMC/C-R composites, which seem to benefit from the randomly fibre reinforced ply, have a higher and little varying flexural stiffness. More dispersed results were also obtained in the SMC/C-R discs, which probably is related with the higher surface waviness caused by material shrinkage during cooling seen in these discs after moulding. In fact, it was not possible to prevent completely the warping of the SMC/C-R discs in this work. In the case of the C/PC discs, the higher stiffness and lower coefficient of expansion of the carbon fibres lead to improve the dimensional stability.

Fig. 4: Stiffness of the C/PC and SMC/C-R discs against fibre orientation

As Fig. 4 also shows, for both composites the stiffness (C_R) increases with the fibre orientation angle, γ , up to 30° . Thus, considering the symmetry of the loading case (Fig. 2), it is possible to infer that the disc stiffness is a periodic function of the angle γ . This means that both discs are expected to show maximum stiffness values in the three point-bending test when the continuous fibres are oriented at angles of $\gamma = 30 \pm n \times 60^\circ$, n being an integer, as can be seen from Fig. 5 for the C/PC discs.

Fig. 5: Flexural stiffness of the C/PC composite discs as a function of γ .

Figures 6 and 7 show the influence of moulding temperature on the flexural stiffness obtained in the C/PC and SMC/C-R discs, respectively. As can be seen from Fig. 6, the moulding temperature does not influence significantly the flexural behaviour of the C/PC discs. In fact, the average result at each orientation falls inside the standard deviations of the values obtained at the different temperatures. These findings are in agreement with the near insensitive flexural behaviour of polycarbonate mouldings with respect to processing temperature [14].

Figure 6: Influence of moulding temperature on the C/PC disc stiffness

Nevertheless, it was possible to notice a lower flexural performance of the SMC/C-R discs at 160 °C (Fig. 7). This result is in agreement with the processing temperature range recommended by the SMC manufacturer (145 °C to 155 °C), and is probably related with the voiding resulting from premature cure of the polyester during the press closing at this temperature.

Figure 6: Influence of the moulding temperature on the SMC/C-R disc stiffness

Finally, the flexural stiffness experimentally obtained for the C/PC and SMC/C-R discs are compared with those predicted upon using the software Algor in Fig. 7. In both cases, the Algor simulations confirm the increase of the flexural stiffness with the fibre orientation (γ) between 0° and 30° . In spite of the FEM software being able to describe this trend, as Fig. 7 also shows, the software predictions are some 13 % below the experimental data for the C/PC discs. Three reasons may explain this difference. In the first place, the raw materials' data used to predict the ply properties utilised in the simulations are not accurate. Also, in the simulations the forces are applied in single points, which is not the case of the tests. Finally, and contrarily to the tests which are carried in the deformation mode, the simulations consider the application of a static force.

Figure 7: Comparison between the experimental and predicted data

In the case of the SMC/C-R discs, a better agreement was found between experimental and predicted stiffness results. In fact, as the variability of the experimental is larger, all the predicted values fall inside the standard deviation determined from the tests. However, it appears that the simulations predict a lower increment of stiffness with the fibre orientation angle. This may derive from the theoretical assumption of complete isotropy in the randomly fibre reinforced ply, which does not correspond exactly to the reality.

CONCLUSIONS

Because of the inherent anisotropy, it is usually difficult to predict the mechanical behaviour of moulded composites plates loaded in complex bending conditions. The bending situation studied in this work showed that the use of randomly reinforced layers in the laminate may increase the mechanical performance of composites subjected to multidirectional stresses and/or strains. The fibre orientation should be optimised for better mechanical performance of the composite plates as required in many bending situations. In this aspect, finite element programs, such as Algor, may be successfully used to optimise the composite fibre orientation and laminate stacking sequence. However, this work also showed that FEM analysis does not predict accurately the flexural performance of moulded anisotropic composite plates, as it depends on several factors, such as processing temperature, surface waviness and loading conditions.

REFERENCES

1. Saarela, O., *LAMDA-LAMinate Design and Analysis*, Helsinki University of Technology, Otaniemi/Finland, 1992.
2. Tsai, S. W., *Composites Design*, Think Composites, USA, 1987.
3. Bassali, W. A., "The Transverse Flexure of Thin Elastic Supported at Several Points", *Proc. Cambr. Phil. Soc.*, Vol. 53, 1957, pp. 728-748.
4. Pouzada, A. S., *A Study on the Design Data and Methods for Plate Like Injection Moulded Thermoplastics Products*, PhD Thesis, Loughborough University of Technology, Loughborough, U. K., 1982.
5. Pouzada, A. S. and Stevens, M. J., "Methods of Generating Flexure Design Data for Injection Moulded Plates", *Plastics and Rubber Proc. and Appl.*, Vol. 4, 1984, pp. 181-187.
6. Gant, B. W., *The Thermoplastic Coating of Carbon Fibers*, M. Sc. Thesis, Clemson University, Clemson, USA, 1987.
7. Gant, B. W., Edie, D. D., Lickfield, G. C., Drews, M. J. and Elliso, M. S., "Thermoplastic Coating of Carbon Fibers", *ASTM STP 1004*, 1989, pp. 50-61.
8. Klett, J. W., *Towpreg Formation for Carbon/Carbon Composites*, M. Sc. Thesis, Clemson University, Clemson, USA, 1991.

9. Klett, J. W., Albiger, J., Edie, D. D. and Lickfield, G. C., "Production and Evaluation of a Polyimide/Carbon Fiber Powder-Coated Towpreg", *Proceedings of the 7th Int. Conf. on Carbon – Carbon '92*, Essen, Germany, 1992, pp. 683-685.
10. Nunes, J. P., Edie, D. D., Bernardo, C. A. and Pouzada, A. S "Formation and Characterization of Carbon/polycarbonate Towpregs", *Proc. of the Tenth Int. Conf. on Composite Materials-ICCM 10*, Whistler, Canada, 1995, Vol. III: Processing and Manufacturing, Poursartip, A. and Street, K.N., Eds, pp. 333-340.
11. Nunes, J. P., Bernardo, C. A., Pouzada, A. S and Edie, D. D., "Formation and Characterization of Carbon/polycarbonate Towpregs and Composites", *Journal of Composite Materials*, Vol. 31, No. 17, 1997, pp. 1758-1777.
12. Nunes, J. P., *A Study of the Processing and Properties of Sheet Molding Compounds and Unidirectional Carbon Fibre Towpregs*, Ph. D. Thesis, University of Minho, Portugal, 1998.
13. Jones, R. M., *Mechanics of Composite Materials*, Scripta Book Company, Washington, 1975
14. Neves, N. M., *Application of Subcomponents to the Design with Amorphous Thermoplastics*, M.Sc. Thesis, University of Minho, Guimarães, Portugal, 1993.